

Fig. S6 flowering

Fig. S6. Morphometric PCA plot of nine informative flowering traits for putative *C. howellii* in downward lavender triangles, *C. howellii* in purple triangles, *C. leichtlinii* ssp. *suksdorfii* in green diamonds, *C. quamash* ssp. *breviflora* in blue circles). Broad-scale analysis (417 plants, 6-8 sites of three putative taxa), PC1-2 =61%. See D3 of CFP sites only (PC1-2 =58%). Traits in Appendix 2; sites in Table 1, Fig. 2 map.